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Abstract

We construct a replication of the approach to momentum factor creation that retains higher path of memory than the usual approaches, producing the full path dependence for sorting criterion. The memory effect is achieved by fractional differencing and results in the trade-off between pure momentum and pure reversal factors. The results of testing show presence large risk-adjusted premium after accounting for market frictions and usual portfolio management constraints such as tracking error restriction and hedging requirements. The outperformance results are robust to potential issues in practical implementation and are excessive to the known risk premia.

Keywords: Momentum Factor, Reversal Factor, Fractional Differencing, Bayesian Machine Learning, Equal Risk Contribution, Investment Strategy

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1 Introduction

In this semester, paper we follow the approach and strategy construction for improved Momentum factor from Soros Chitsiripanich et al. (2022), who apply the fractional differencing technique to prices of stocks, which then provides the more optimal sorting of chosen assets. We follow the fractional differencing technique from Marcos Lopez de Prado (2018).

1.1 Momentum Strategies

The momentum effect in financial markets refers to the empirical observation that assets which have performed well in the recent past (typically over a 3- to 12-month horizon) tend to continue performing well in the near future, while assets that have performed poorly tend to continue performing poorly. This phenomenon, often summarized as "winners keep winning and losers keep losing," stands as one of the most pervasive and well-documented market anomalies, challenging the efficient market hypothesis in its weaker forms.

The seminal work formalizing this effect in equity markets is often attributed to Jegadeesh and Titman (1993), who demonstrated that strategies buying past winners and selling past losers generated significant abnormal returns in the U.S. stock market. Subsequent research has confirmed the presence of momentum across various asset classes, including international equities (Rouwenhorst (1998)), commodities (Erb et al. (2006)), currencies (Okunev et al. 2003), and bonds (Asness et al. (2013)), as well as across different time horizons.

Common implementations of momentum strategies typically involve:

- **Lookback Period:** Ranking assets based on their cumulative returns over a specified past period (e.g., the previous 6 or 12 months). To avoid capturing very short-term reversal effects, often the most recent month's return is skipped.
- **Sorting:** Dividing the ranked assets into quantiles (e.g., deciles or quintiles).
- **Portfolio Formation:** Constructing portfolios by taking long positions in the top-performing quantile (winners) and often, though not always, short positions in the bottom-performing quantile (losers). Simpler long-only versions will focus solely on the winner portfolio.
- **Holding Period:** Maintaining these positions for a specific subsequent period (e.g., 1 to 12 months) before rebalancing.

Despite its apparent simplicity and historical profitability, the momentum premium is not without its puzzles and challenges. It exhibits periods of significant underperformance, notably "momentum crashes" (Daniel et al. (2016)), which often occur during market reversals or periods of high volatility. The underlying drivers of the momentum effect are also a subject of ongoing debate, with explanations ranging from behavioral biases such as investor underreaction to initial news and subsequent overreaction (Hong et al. (1999) and Barberis et al. (1998)), to risk-based explanations where momentum captures exposure to time-varying systematic risks (Johnson (2002)). The persistence of the anomaly, even after its widespread documentation, continues to intrigue researchers and practitioners alike.

1.2 Trade-Off Between Momentum & Reversal

While the momentum effect, as described by strategies focusing on intermediate-term past returns (e.g., 3 to 12 months), is well-documented, financial markets also exhibit reversal patterns. Short-term reversals (e.g., over 1-month horizons) are a known phenomenon, often motivating the skipping of the most recent month in standard momentum calculations (Jegadeesh (1990)). More critically for traditional momentum strategies, long-term reversals (e.g., over 3- to 5-year horizons) suggest that strong past performance eventually tends to revert (De Bondt et al. (1985)). This creates a fundamental trade-off in designing trend-following strategies. Standard momentum strategies, with their fixed lookback windows, are optimized to capture intermediate-term persistence. However, this fixed memory length can make them vulnerable:

1. **Momentum Crashes:** These strategies can suffer severe drawdowns, particularly when market sentiment sharply reverses or after prolonged bull markets where "winner" stocks become excessively overvalued and then correct. The fixed lookback window means the strategy is slow to adapt to a changing regime, continuing to hold onto assets whose positive trend has abruptly ended or reversed. Daniel et al. (2016) highlight how these crashes are often concentrated in periods when past "loser" stocks rebound sharply.
2. **Ignoring Longer-Term Information:** By focusing only on, for instance, the past 12 months, these strategies discard information from the preceding periods. This older information might contain signals about the sustainability of a trend or the early stages of a longer-term reversal.
3. **Abrupt Weight Changes:** The "all-or-nothing" nature of fixed-window cut-offs for information (data within the window is fully considered, data outside is fully ignored) can lead to less stable signals.

The length of the lookback period (memory) is crucial. A very short lookback might be dominated by noise or short-term reversals. An intermediate lookback, as commonly used, captures the momentum premium. However, a strategy that can dynamically or smoothly incorporate a longer history, giving decaying importance to older data, might better navigate the complex interplay between persistence and mean-reversion. Such an approach could potentially mitigate the severity of momentum crashes by being more sensitive to the early signs of trend exhaustion or by inherently balancing the shorter-term momentum signal with longer-term rever-sionary pressures.

This paper explores fractional differencing as a method to achieve such a nuanced memory structure. By allowing the differencing order d to be a non-integer, we can create a signal that retains memory of the entire past price path, with weights that decay smoothly rather than being truncated abruptly. This, we hypothesize, allows for a more robust factor that can better balance the persistent nature of momentum with the eventual tendency towards reversal, leading to a more stable and potentially enhanced risk-adjusted performance.

1.3 Strategy Outline

This paper constructs and analyzes a momentum-based investment strategy that utilizes fractional differencing to achieve a more persistent memory structure in signal generation. Our approach aims to improve upon traditional momentum factor construction by creating a sorting criterion with full path dependence, thereby potentially offering a better trade-off between capturing momentum and mitigating reversal risks.

The core methodology involves the following key steps:

1. **Signal Generation via Fractional Differencing:** We apply fractional differencing to the time series of historical log-prices for each stock in our universe. The differencing order, d , is chosen to be less than 1 (specifically, $d = 0.9$ in our primary analysis, following insights from related literature and preliminary investigations indicating a favorable balance of memory retention). This process yields a fractionally differenced price series for each asset.
2. **Return Forecasting:** We forecast one-step-ahead returns based on the assumption that the fractionally differenced price series are covariance stationary. The forecast relies on the unconditional mean of this transformed series, which is then inverted back to a predicted log-return, incorporating the entire available price history with decaying weights.
3. **Universe and Portfolio Construction:** The strategy is tested on a universe of U.S. equities, focusing on a subset of the 5,000 most liquid stocks from CRSP

to ensure tradability. At each rebalancing point, stocks are ranked based on their forecasted returns. We then form a long-only portfolio by selecting the top quintile (i.e., $q = 0.2$) of stocks in our baseline analysis, and subsequently refine this to the top 5% ($q = 0.05$) for our main implementable strategy, holding approximately 125 stocks. Portfolio constituents are equally weighted.

- 4. Rebalancing and Analysis Horizon:** The portfolio is rebalanced on a weekly basis. Our primary analysis window for calculating unconditional means is $T = 250$ trading days. The backtesting period spans from March 2004 to March 2022.
- 5. Performance Evaluation:** The strategy's performance is evaluated against standard benchmarks, including the S&P 500 and a traditional 6-month momentum strategy. We assess risk-adjusted returns, alpha generation relative to common factors, and robustness through various subsample and sensitivity analyses, accounting for transaction costs. Implementability considerations, such as hedging and volatility control, are also explored.

By employing fractional differencing, we aim to create a momentum signal that is less susceptible to the abrupt cutoffs of fixed-window methods, potentially leading to more stable and robust performance.

1.4 What is the inefficiency that we exploit?

The proposed fractional momentum strategy aims to capitalize on market inefficiencies that are primarily rooted in behavioral finance theories and the nuanced way information is impounded into asset prices. While traditional momentum strategies also tap into these, we argue that the use of fractional differencing allows for a more refined exploitation of these inefficiencies.

Key potential sources of exploitable inefficiency include:

- 1. Slow Information Diffusion and Underreaction:** Information, particularly firm-specific news or broader economic shifts, may not be instantaneously and fully incorporated into asset prices. Investors might initially underreact to new information, leading to trends that persist as the information gradually disseminates and is processed by a wider range of market participants Hong et al. (1999). Fractional differencing, by retaining a long memory with decaying weights, is well-suited to capture these gradual price adjustments that extend beyond typical short-to-intermediate momentum windows. It systematically gives more weight to recent manifestations of the trend while still accounting for its earlier development.

2. **Herding and Positive Feedback Trading:** As a trend develops, some investors may engage in herding behavior or positive feedback trading, buying assets simply because their prices have been rising. This can prolong trends beyond fundamental justifications in the medium term. The path-dependent nature of fractional momentum, which aggregates the entire history of price movements, can effectively model these self-reinforcing dynamics.
3. **Disposition Effect and Anchoring:** Investors often exhibit a disposition effect, namely a reluctance to sell assets that have depreciated (losers) and an eagerness to sell assets that have appreciated (winners) too soon (Shefrin et al. (1985)). They may also anchor their valuation expectations to past price levels. These biases can slow down the adjustment of prices to their fundamental values, contributing to momentum. Fractional differencing implicitly captures the "weight of history" that such anchoring might reflect.
4. **Mitigation of Overreaction and Reversal Sensitivity:** While exploiting underreaction, the smooth decay of influence from past prices in a fractionally-differenced series might also make the signal less prone to the sharp "whipsaws" that can occur with fixed-window momentum when a trend abruptly ends and reverses. Standard momentum, by forgetting everything beyond its lookback period, can be caught flat-footed by such reversals. Fractional momentum's "long memory" potentially allows it to be more sensitive to the gradual fading of a trend or the early signs of a long-term reversal, providing a more adaptive response than a fixed-window approach. This is crucial for navigating the trade-off between momentum and reversal discussed earlier.

In essence, we hypothesize that the market does not perfectly and instantly incorporate all information, nor does it assign optimal weights to historical price movements when forming expectations. Fractional differencing provides a systematic, model-free way to construct a momentum signal that reflects a more persistent and smoothly weighted aggregation of past price information. This, in turn, allows for a more robust capture of trends driven by the gradual resolution of uncertainty and the behavioral patterns of investors, while potentially being more resilient to the inherent noise and regime shifts in financial markets.

2 Literature Review

Momentum is one of the most robust and widely documented anomalies in financial markets. Seminal work by Jegadeesh and Titman 1993 showed that strategies which buy past winners and sell past losers yield significant excess returns. These findings challenged the Efficient Market Hypothesis and were later supported by Fama and French (1996), who showed that momentum cannot be explained by traditional risk-based models. Research has since confirmed that momentum exists across asset classes, as shown in Asness, Moskowitz, and Pedersen (2013). Their findings also highlight that momentum can be effectively combined with other factors, such as value and size, to improve diversification and portfolio efficiency. Importantly, momentum is not a US-specific phenomenon. Studies such as Rouwenhorst (1998) and Griffin, Ji, and Martin (2003) show that momentum is a global phenomenon, observed across equity markets in both developed and emerging economies, with only weak correlation between countries, which indicates country-specific drivers.

Despite its strong historical performance, traditional momentum strategies face several limitations. They are prone to high turnover, suffer during market reversals, and often exhibit negative timing with market cycles. These issues limit their net performance and applicability in real-world portfolios. This work builds on the growing literature addressing these weaknesses by proposing a fractional momentum strategy, based on fractional differencing techniques introduced by López de Prado (2018) and further developed in Chitsiripanich et al. (2024). The latter demonstrate that this strategy allows us to preserve long-memory properties in financial time series while achieving stationarity, leading to more stable and informative momentum signals. The results indicate that fractional momentum improves risk-adjusted performance, reduces volatility, and mitigates market timing biases, while maintaining near-zero market beta in hedged implementations. To address transaction cost challenges, we draw on recent advancements by Chitsiripanich et al. (2024), who introduce path-dependent portfolio constraints. These techniques reduce portfolio turnover by 95-99%, aligning daily strategies with the stability of monthly rebalancing, and significantly improving net returns under realistic trading conditions. Additionally, our implementation incorporates volatility timing, inspired by Moreira and Muir (2017). Their research shows that volatility-managed portfolios can offer superior Sharpe ratios by scaling exposure dynamically-taking less risk in turbulent periods while still capturing high average returns. This approach enhances both the robustness and performance consistency of the strategy.

In summary, prior literature confirms that momentum is a persistent, global, and cross-asset anomaly that can be enhanced when combined with other factors. The fractional momentum framework leverages these insights and introduces a novel way to extract the momentum premium more efficiently, with stronger risk management and reduced trading frictions.

3 Strategy Description

3.1 Fractional Differencing

Fractional differencing generalizes the concept of classical differencing in time series analysis. While integer differencing removes deterministic trends or seasonality (e.g., $\Delta X_t = X_t - X_{t-1}$), fractional differencing allows the differencing order d to be a real number, enabling more nuanced control over memory and stationarity in time series. It is defined via the binomial series expansion:

$$(1 - B)^d X_t = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{d}{k} (-1)^k X_{t-k},$$

where B is the backshift operator and $\binom{d}{k}$ is the generalized binomial coefficient. The order d determines the influence of past observations: $d = 0$ retains the raw series; $d = 1$ yields the first difference; values $0 < d < 1$ interpolate between these extremes, allowing long-memory behavior.

This formulation is central to the construction of the *fractional momentum* signal. Unlike traditional momentum—typically calculated as a simple return over a fixed horizon—fractional momentum aggregates past returns with power-law weighting. Applying fractional differencing to log prices results in a return-like series where recent information is emphasized, yet long-term trends remain partially visible.

Figure 1: Fractional Difference Weights on Prices

3.2 Return Forecasting

The construction of return forecasts using fractional differencing involves a three-step transformation process. For a set of m assets with log-prices $p_t = (p_{t,1}, \dots, p_{t,m})$, we first apply the fractional difference operator $(1 - B)^d$ to obtain the fractionally differenced series:

$$\tilde{p}_{t,i} = (1 - B)^d p_{t,i} = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \pi_s p_{t-s,i},$$

where B is the backshift operator and π_s are the weights from the binomial expansion. The weights are defined as $\pi_0 = 1$ and $\pi_s = (-1)^s \prod_{i=0}^{s-1} \frac{d-i}{s!}$ for $s > 0$.

Under the assumption of covariance stationarity, we estimate the unconditional mean μ_i using the sample average:

$$\hat{\mu}_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (1 - B)^d p_{t,i} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \tilde{p}_{t,i} \quad (1)$$

The one-step ahead prediction for the fractionally differenced series is then:

$$\hat{\tilde{p}}_{T+1|T,i} = \hat{\mu}_i$$

To obtain the predicted log-return, we invert the fractional difference formula to get the predicted log-price:

$$\hat{p}_{T+1|T,i} = \hat{\tilde{p}}_{T+1|T,i} - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \pi_s p_{T+1-s,i} = \hat{\mu}_i - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \pi_s p_{T+1-s,i}$$

Finally, the predicted log-return is computed as:

$$\hat{r}_{T+1,i} = \hat{p}_{T+1|T,i} - p_{T,i} = \hat{\mu}_i + (d - 1)p_{T,i} - \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \pi_s p_{T+1-s,i}$$

This three-step transformation process differs from the classical momentum approach, which uses a single-step conversion from prices to returns. When $d = 1$, we see that our approach collapses to the standard momentum strategy, but for $d \in [0, 1)$, it incorporates information from all available price data in the prediction.

3.3 Stationarity Testing

The validity of our approach relies on the assumption that the fractionally differenced log-price series $\tilde{p}_{t,i} = (1 - B)^d p_{t,i}$ is covariance stationary, meaning it has a constant unconditional mean $\mu_i = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{p}_{t,i}]$. Under this assumption, the estimator $\hat{\mu}_i$ in equation 1 is consistent.

We emphasize that without stationarity, the use of sample averages $\hat{\mu}_i$ as forecasts becomes unreliable, and the foundational assumption behind our return prediction method breaks down.

To assess whether a time series is stationary, we begin by applying the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. This test checks for the presence of a unit root, where the null hypothesis assumes the series is non-stationary. If we reject the null, it suggests that the series is stationary—that is, its statistical properties such as the mean and variance remain stable over time.

This analysis is often complemented by the Kwiatkowski–Phillips–Schmidt–Shin (KPSS) test, which takes the opposite approach. The KPSS test assumes the series is stationary around a deterministic trend (trend-stationary) as its null hypothesis. Rejecting this null implies the presence of a unit root or another form of non-stationarity.

Using both tests together gives a clearer picture of the series’ behavior. For instance, if the ADF test rejects the null (indicating no unit root) and the KPSS test does not (supporting trend-stationarity), we can be fairly confident the series is stationary. On the other hand, if ADF fails to reject and KPSS rejects, there’s stronger evidence the series is non-stationary. If the two tests conflict or results are inconclusive, additional investigation or transformation (such as differencing) may be necessary.

We present the results of our testing on the obtained data. This testing is done in-sample, as we do not select the stocks for the strategy, based on stationarity tests, but rather use those to make sure that estimator is correct.

Table 1: % of Rejected (Non-Stationary) Stocks (03/2005-03/2022).

Level	ADF Test	KPSS Test
10% Significance	0.00%	0.00%
5% Significance	0.00%	70.65%
1% Significance	0.00%	90.36%

Figure 2: Example of Fractionally Differenced Price, General Electric (Ticker: GE)

3.4 An Intuitive Financial Interpretation of Fractional Momentum

Fractional momentum can be intuitively understood as a smoother, memory-aware generalization of traditional momentum. While standard momentum relies on recent returns over a fixed lookback window, fractional momentum integrates the entire return history using power law decaying weights. This approach gives greater importance to recent data but does not discard older information abruptly.

From a behavioral finance perspective, this aligns with known investor biases such as slow information diffusion. Investors often place more weight on recent trends while still being influenced by long-term price anchors. Fractional momentum effectively captures this behavioral pattern.

Moreover, this method reduces susceptibility to short-term noise and avoids the regime-switching pitfalls associated with fixed-window momentum strategies. It creates a natural continuum between short-term technical signals and long-term trend following approaches, thereby generalizing momentum across time scales.

3.5 Portfolio Construction

Following the approach in Soros Chitsiripanich et al. (2022), we employ the similar portfolio construction logic:

1. We obtain return predictions $\hat{r}_{T+1,i}$ for each stock i , as outlined in the Return Forecasting section.
2. We sort the stocks in the ascending order by return predictions. For main experiments we use 20%-quantiles, meaning that we end up with 5 buckets: "Low", 2, 3, 4, "High". In this ranking "High" corresponds to largest predicted return.
3. We take long "High" quantile stocks with equal weights and take short "Low" quantile stocks with equal weights at each rebalancing period.

We estimate all of the parameters fully out-of-sample, using only available prices at the point of rebalancing with 1 day lag. We use weekly rebalancing to match the analysis of the paper, however, our tests show that outperformance still holds for daily and monthly rebalancing frequencies.

4 Strategy Analysis

This Section analyses different variations of the strategy implementation. We target **long-only** equally-weighted strategy on a reasonably liquid subset of available stocks with futures hedging / volatility control. Even though we will also present a long-short version for reference, the main emphasis is on the implementable strategy, which is long leg with hedging and / or risk control.

As a baseline, we take the 6 months simple momentum strategy similar to Jegadeesh and Titman (1993), where we sort all available for trading stocks by cumulative log-return for the past 6 months and take the same quantile as in our core strategy. For the reference to the wide market, we use S&P500, replicated by the S&P500 Futures + Risk-Free rate, which is motivated by the trading setup for 2025-2026. Additionally, we test sorting stock in 6-month Momentum by both the cumulative return and the volatility-standardized cumulative return to address excessive momentum as opposed to the usual movements for some high volatility stocks. We find that the latter approach results in improved performance (which is supported by the similar methodology of iShares ETF for Momentum), that is why we use it as a stronger baseline.

Throughout this Section, we **use** $T = 250$ as a **window size** for unconditional mean $\hat{\mu}_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \tilde{p}_{t,i}$. It is chosen to be constant in the analysis, being in line with the paper that uses the same value for this hyperparameter and the overall literature on momentum.

The main experiments of this Section are focused on **weekly rebalancing**, modeled by fixed window of 5 days for rebalancing, where for each point the whole history is available. It is motivated both by the main paper findings and the practical implementation approach. We outline the in-sample analysis of outperformance sensitivity to the rebalancing period in Appendix B. We find that the rebalancing period does not affect the fact of outperformance, but rather affects the size of such outperformance.

We start with fixing $q = 0.2$ for the 20%-quantile to match the approach, used in the paper. Quantile analysis will be performed in the end of this Section.

For transaction costs, we use the usual assumptions of trading with 3 bps brokerage fee and 2 bps average bid-ask spread. The brokerage fee is applied for S&P futures too, while rollover costs are embedded in the initial data from Bloomberg.

4.1 Data

In this paper, we focus on the universe of US stocks for the purposes of the realistic portfolio implementation. However, further analysis might be extended to other momentum-exhibiting asset classes such as commodities and cryptocurrencies and to another stocks universes, subject to availability for trading implementation.

The data we use is from Center for Research in Securities Prices (CRSP). We filter stocks by being listed at NYSE, AMEX, and NASDAQ (CRSP exchange codes 1, 2, 3). Additionally, we use a subset of only ordinary common shares (CRSP shares codes 10 and 11), exactly as it is done in the paper. We end up with the sample ranging from March 2004 to March 2022 of daily frequency adjusted prices (we use ‘cfacpr’ field for adjustment) and returns (pre-calculated by CRSP), totaling 12,872 securities.

For hedging purposes, we use excess return on S&P500 Futures (Ticker ‘ES1 Index’) from Bloomberg (GFUT function) for the same time period under consideration. We use rollover-adjusted (by ratio factor) daily prices, where the rollover is done in one day and is taken relative to first notice.

The factor data is taken from the website for the Jensen et al. (2021) paper. We get daily factor returns for our analysis period, restricting to Size, Value, Momentum and Low-Risk (Low-Beta) as meaningful subset of factors. The risk-free rate used is daily accrued risk-free rate from Kenneth French library.

We focus our analysis on three sub-universes of the obtained sample, narrowing down to more tradeable samples:

1. Full sample of 12,872 securities - proof of concept sample, aiming to match the paper. It includes all the stocks from CRSP, meaning that we end up with potentially very illiquid stocks.
2. Subsample of 5,000 most liquid securities - it is obtained by sorting **in-sample** all the stocks with average trading volume in dollars. We take the first 5,000 stocks of such sorting (with \$3,750,395.94 being the average daily volume threshold for filtering in this case). The number 5,000 is motivated by the attainable universe of iShares MSCI USA Momentum Factor ETF (Ticker ‘MTUM’), which outlines 3,510 stocks to be in the attainable universe at the time of writing. Therefore, as we choose 5,000 stocks for the whole sample, we aim to achieve not more than 3,510 stocks, available for trading. We argue that even though such selection is done in-sample, it leaks virtually no information to the strategy, because a company that have been trading 3 days with high volume and then went into bankruptcy would have the same average dollar volume as the stock that was trading with the same high volume in the whole sample. However, further analysis with out-of-sample sorting on subsample has showed that this detail does not affect the performance significantly.

3. S&P500 constituents - even though such a sample virtually guarantees the liquidity, we claim that it is an excessive restriction, which significantly affects the performance. It is an expected behaviour though, as S&P500 stocks have been largely driven by the passive investment flows, which are pro-momentum due to rebalancing to capitalization-dependent (i.e., price-dependent) target weights. As our strategy aims to balance momentum and mean-reversion signals, this results in slightly deteriorated, but still significant outperformance.

4.2 Universe analysis

First of all, we start with the strategy performance on the full sample of 12,872 US Stocks. This approach serves as paper replication and proof of concept, so we expect outperformance compared to both the baseline and S&P500 futures.

Figure 3: Cumulative Performance with TC, $T = 250$, $q = 0.2$, Full US Stocks (03/2005-03/2022)

We can see that not only is the outperformance is higher, but also that the Fractional Momentum strategy exhibits a larger positive slope, indicating that outperformance is not driven by the compounding effect, accumulated during 2008 GFC, which appears early in the sample. This result is in line with the paper findings.

As was outlined earlier, the universe here contains excessive number of illiquid stocks.

However, restricting the universe to a liquid subsample, the outperformance is retained, while the order of outperformance is smaller as expected.

Figure 4: Cumulative Performance with TC, $T = 250$, $q = 0.2$, Liquid US Stocks (03/2005-03/2022)

However, we argue that the comparison with the S&P500 is not exactly correct, as, while it retains implementability, the actual universe that is allowed for strategy selection in this testing is much wider, hinting towards potential outperformance explanation via Size factor loading. While one could suspect outperformance is driven by the excessive Momentum in lower capitalization stocks, the experiment shows that **Fractional Momentum strategy turns out to be still superior to usual Momentum construction.**

Therefore, as a next step we test the same two strategies performance against the Equally Weighted portfolio of 5,000 Top Liquid Stocks. While one should note that this strategy is hardly implementable in practice due to operational restrictions and minimum lot size requirements (because each stock gets assigned $w = 0.02\%$), it represents a reasonable baseline for theoretical exploration.

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Figure 5: Cumulative Performance with TC, $T = 250$, $q = 0.2$, Top Liquid Stocks (03/2005-03/2022)

Figure 6: Cumulative Performance with TC, $T = 250$, $q = 0.2$, S&P500 Constituents (03/2005-03/2022)

Finally, we finish the experiments with the strategy test on subset of S&P500 stocks by looking before each rebalancing period at the stocks that are included in the

index at that date and running the analysis on this subset only. While this approach definitely solves any liquidity concerns, we argue that it is too restrictive for both Momentum and Fractional Momentum, especially in light of outperformance of large cap stocks in recent years.

Summarizing, we find that the **Fractional Momentum outperforms out-of-sample** the usual approaches to Momentum factor construction and to the benchmarks. However, being too restrictive to the strategy results in more volatile PnL profile, resulting in large drawdowns during GFC, from which the strategy was able to recover and outperform only in recent years. One of the reasons for that we have noted is that due to being long-only, our strategy sometimes obtains only negative signals, but by construction has to take the "least negative" stocks into the portfolio. The tests that restrict the chosen set to be minimum of upper quantile and number of non-zero predicted returns in sorting exhibit worse performance due to imperfect prediction of the sign of the future returns from this procedure.

Importantly, the presented approach is **fully out-of-sample, except for the liquid stocks selection**. As argued before, this does not shift the strategy logic, and out-of-sample choice testing support robustness of our strategy to this simplification. As this analysis shows, the 5,000 Liquid Stocks sample represents robust and implementable trade-off between the wideness of the universe and the liquidity of the chosen universe. Therefore, **we fix this universe for the further analysis**.

Table 2: FD OOS Strategies on different universes (03/2005-03/2022) after TC with weekly rebalancing, $T = 250$, $quantile = 20\%$.

Strategy	SR	Annualized Alpha	IR
Full US Stocks	1.3132	43.23% (0.00**)	1.5698
5000 Liquid US	0.8758	37.92% (0.00**)	1.3048
S&P500 Constituents	0.2448	9.14% (0.12)	0.3426

Table outlines Sharpe Ratio, Alpha to Factor Loadings, and Information Ratio to Factor Loadings.

* indicates statistical significance at 5%. ** indicates statistical significance at 1%.

4.3 Liquid US Shrinkage

As we have seen in the previous results, the usual approach results in noisy values of the estimates, while being somewhat useful for the ranking performance. Therefore, the natural idea would be to try to improve the estimates by being more conservative than the initial strategy suggests.

The next step for the analysis attempts to robustify the prediction by Random Matrix Theory-based method for return estimators shrinkage from Bodnar et al. (2019).

At each rebalancing period we augment the existing procedure by running the shrinkage and estimation on the series of fractionally differenced prices.

Figure 7: Cumulative Performance with TC, $T = 250$, $q = 0.2$, BOP Shrinkage (03/2005-03/2022)

The shrinkage does not introduce any significant change in the performance, as outlined in the Summary Performance figures. Therefore, one may conclude that the FD estimator is already robust enough for sorting purposes.

4.4 Liquid US ERC

As we can note from the results on all of the universes, our strategy exhibits superior Sharpe Ratio, producing more significant risk premia on each unit of risk. However, the amount of risk that the strategy exhibits is also excessive, if compared to both S&P500 and 6-month Momentum. That is why we want to attempt robustification of the results via risk control in the chosen universe. Namely, after selecting the upper quantile we substitute the equal weights to the risk-minimizing set of weights, achieved by Hierarchical Risk Parity. We follow the approach from the initial paper Marcos López de Prado (2016).

Additionally, we refer here to our discussion with Dr. Soros Chitsiripanich. As usually stated in the literature, there is no statistically significant relation between volatility of the stock and momentum of the same stock. This means that such HRP approach will likely not underweigh high-momentum stocks and not deteriorate the initial strategy logic.

Figure 8: Cumulative Performance, HRP (02/2005-03/2022)

We can note that the performance if such a strategy is highly inferior to the usual Fractional Momentum both in volatility and the return. Therefore, we can conclude that risk-adjusting weights only introduce additional noise, even if using the state-of-the-art approach for denoised optimization. Thus we argue that the risk control should be exogenous to the cross-sectional weights construction, which can be attained by picking the amount of capital placed into the strategy at each rebalancing date, while keeping the existing logic for cross-sectional weights.

4.5 Volatility Scaling

First of all, to support the argument above we test the In-Sample scaling of the volatility, as is usually done in the literature. We scale down the strategy variance to target the S&P500 variance to be implementable for tracking error-seeking investment schemes. This is done by applying the rescaling weight to each rebalancing

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point of the strategy:

$$w^{scale} = \frac{\sigma_{SPX}^2}{\sigma_{Strategy}^2}$$

where each estimator is calculated on the whole sample:

$$\sigma_j^2 = \sigma^2(r_{0:end}^j)$$

We then apply the attained estimator to excess return of the strategy and add up the risk-free rate:

$$\tilde{r}^2 = w^{scaled} r^{excess} + r f$$

Figure 9: Cumulative Performance, In-Sample Scaling (02/2005-03/2022)

As this approach is performing as expected due to linear scaling, meaning that the risk-premium-to-risk ratio is preserved under such transformation, this makes a good case for us to approach the Out-Of-Sample scaling by backward-looking variance estimator at each rebalancing period, using all historical datapoints that were available at the time of choosing the weights:

$$w_{\tau}^{scale} = \frac{\sigma^2(r_{0:\tau-1}^{SPX})}{\sigma^2(r_{0:\tau-1}^{Strategy})}$$

Figure 10: Cumulative Performance, Out-Of-Sample Scaling (02/2005-03/2022)

As one may note, the strategy exhibits inferior metrics, compared to the base Fractional Momentum strategy. This is in line with the expectation, as by adjusting the weight in the strategy dynamically, we introduce imperfect rebalancing - when the stocks in the market exhibit successive momentum periods, the volatility is usually also elevated in these particular stocks. It means that our strategy decreases the upper quantile exposure during these high volatility periods, sacrificing the performance for the lower risk. However, we still consider such a result valuable from the overall risk-management perspective.

An alternative approach would be to manage this trade-off in the constant allocation fashion. As we know that Fractional Momentum exhibits high volatility in general by construction (which is also supported by our further subsampling analysis in this Section), one might choose to allocate the constant out-of-sample weight to the strategy, aiming to match S&P500. We demonstrate this procedure by the arbitrarily chosen sample split: we calculate the ratio of volatilities in similar fashion for the period 03/2005-01/2016 and allocate constant percentage to the strategy, testing the performance for 01/2016-03/2022.

Figure 11: Cumulative Performance, OOS Volatility Scaling (01/2016-03/2022)

We see that the dynamically adjusted strategy (our approach above) produces better out-of-sample performance than this constant allocation. Therefore, while one might indeed conclude from the previous analysis that constant allocation is a good alternative for risk-management, it turns out that we do not know out-of-sample the true ratio of volatility. In other words, for Fractional Momentum the out-performance comes inherently with the higher volatility. Thus, either one agrees for conditional rebalancing that causes inferior performance, or takes the strategy with the elevated volatility as it is.

4.6 Quantile Analysis

In the following subsection, we aim to challenge our approach from implementation point of view. Indeed, even though, the new 5,000 universe still argues in favor of the introduced strategy, the practical implementation raises concerns towards chosen $q = 0.2$. While this number is consistent with the paper findings, one might be tempted to test it in the analysis.

However, we argue that the trade-off between quantile and performance here is going to be as usual - the lower the quantile, the better the performance in terms of Sharpe Ratio and higher the volatility. While we avoid testing the optimal quantile in-sample, the optimal one is actually dictated by the realistic implementation.

As on average, our strategy produces around 2,500 available for selection stocks at each rebalancing date, we can note that $q = 0.2$ results in 500 stocks, available for selection. From practical point of view, the amount is excessive. Therefore, we aim to restrict ourselves to 125 holdings to match the number of current holdings in the iShares Momentum ETF at the time of writing. It corresponds to taking $q = 0.05$, which we present further.

Figure 12: Cumulative Performance 5%-quantile (01/2016-03/2022)

Table 3: OOS Liquid US Stocks On Different Quantiles (03/2005-03/2022) after TC with weekly rebalancing, $T = 250$.

* indicates statistical significance at 5%, ** - at 1%.

Strategy	Annualized Volatility	SR	Annualized Alpha	IR
S&P500 Futures TR	9.23%	0.0816	-	-
Equally Weighted	25.64%	0.8245	23.16% (0.00**)	0.9545
FM Top Liquid $q = 20\%$	36.36%	0.8758	37.92% (0.00**)	1.3048
FM OOS Vol Control $q = 20\%$	4.92%	0.5958	3.15% (0.02*)	0.6865
FM Top Liquid $q = 5\%$	50.56%	1.2663	71.1% (0.00**)	1.5758
FM OOS Vol Control $q = 5\%$	5.02%	0.6302	3.27% (0.02*)	0.6658

We can see that the performance change is in line with the expectations - our volatility is higher and the Sharpe Ratio is higher too.

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Another line of argumentation might concern transaction costs. Even though the presented analysis is post-TC, one might point out that taking larger quantile means that some of the stocks stay in portfolio, thus, the rebalancing costs are lower. The following figures demonstrate that the change of turnover is surely present, but not quite large ($+20\%$ turnover $\implies -0.52\%$ per annum, indicating that mostly the selected long leg is brand new at each point of time).

Figure 13: Turnover 20% quantile (01/2016-03/2022)

Figure 14: Turnover 5%-quantile (01/2016-03/2022)

Concluding the analysis, we will focus on the 5%-quantile as a robust and implementable version of the suggested strategy.

4.7 Futures Hedging

Finally, we conclude our analysis by implementing the replication of the futures hedging that replicates the trading setup for 2025-2026. We apply the hedging to unscaled Fractional Momentum 5%-quantile of Liquid US Stocks. The procedure is as follows:

- We calculate the betas for all stocks that are included in the long leg by backward-looking OLS on 1-year data.
- **Each day** before the next rebalancing day we short $\beta^T w^{trailing}$ futures for $\beta, w^{trailing} \in \mathbb{R}^{125 \times 1}$, where $w^{trailing}$ denotes the trailing weights in the portfolio, accounting for returns between each days via recursive update $w_t^{trailing} = w_{rebal_k}(1 + r_{t-1}) \forall t \in [rebal_k, \dots, rebal_{k+1}]$
- The excess return for the futures is accrued between rebalancing dates and added to the excess return of the strategy at the next day, which is not precisely a correct way to compound (it should be added on daily basis, allowing to be reinvested in stocks), but the change is not significant, while it allows for correct further decoupling of returns of the strategy itself and the hedging mechanism.
- We account for daily accrual of transaction costs for each day of rebalancing the futures position additionally to the main set of costs, associated with stocks.

Table 4: OOS 5%-quantile (03/2005-03/2022) after TC with weekly rebalancing and daily hedging, $T = 250$.

Table outlines Sharpe Ratio, Alpha to Factor Loadings and Information Ratio to Factor Loadings. * indicates statistical significance at 5%, ** indicates statistical significance at 1%.

Strategy	Annualized Volatility	SR	Annualized Alpha	IR	Market Beta
S&P500 Futures TR	9.23%	0.0816	-	-	-
FM Unhedged	50.56%	1.2663	71.1% (0.00**)	1.5758	1.67
FM Hedged	54.33%	0.7154	45.72% (0.00**)	0.9209	1.78
6M Momentum Hedged	30.48%	-0.0677	0.0% (0.66)	-0.01	1.04

Figure 15: Cumulative Performance 5%-quantile (03/2005-03/2022)

The strategy still produces significant outperformance even after hedging. However, one may note that the hedging procedure does not produce any significant decrease in either volatility or beta. This is in line with the expectations. As the trading setup requires daily rebalanced futures hedging, one results with being short on average beta of the portfolio. However, as this is achieved with daily dynamic rebalancing, the actual hedging is not attained - one should have approached this by keeping the weight constant throughout the rebalancings.

Moreover, backward-looking betas produce biased estimates in case of Momentum. As past performance was driven by excessive momentum, the returns of the selected stocks have been diverging from the average stock in the market for a while, meaning that the stock becomes less correlated to market, resulting in lower beta estimate:

$$\beta_i \downarrow = \frac{Cov(r_i, r^{mkt})}{Var(r^{mkt})} = \rho \downarrow \frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_{mkt}}$$

It means that such a hedging approach is usually underhedged for long-only case, resulting in higher beta that would be expected out-of-sample. Such an issue can be solved by dynamic prediction of future realized beta, which is out of scope of this strategy testing.

4.8 Summary Performance

Summarizing this Section, we present the final analysis of all the strategies with **out-of-sample performance after transaction costs**. For full set of metrics please consult the table in Appendix A.

Table 5: OOS Liquid US Stocks Strategies (03/2005-03/2022) after TC with weekly rebalancing, $T = 250$, $quantile = 20\%$ (if not stated otherwise).

Table outlines Sharpe Ratio, Alpha to Factor Loadings and Information Ratio to Factor Loadings. * indicates statistical significance at 5%, ** indicates statistical significance at 1%. Target strategy for implementation is **highlighted**.

Strategy	SR	Annualized Alpha	IR
S&P500 Futures TR	0.0816	-	-
Equally Weighted	0.8245	23.16% (0.00**)	0.9545
6M Momentum	0.8763	36.33% (0.00**)	1.1388
FM Top Liquid	0.8758	37.92% (0.00**)	1.3048
FM Shrinkage	0.8758	37.92% (0.00**)	1.3048
FM Hierarchical RP	0.3788	2.49% (0.18)	0.3758
FM OOS Vol Control	0.5958	3.15% (0.02*)	0.6865
FD Top Liquid $q = 5\%$	1.2663	71.1% (0.00**)	1.5758
FM OOS Vol Control $q = 5\%$	0.6302	3.27% (0.02*)	0.6658
FM Hedged	0.7154	45.72% (0.00**)	0.9209

Table 6: Fractional Momentum Factor Loadings (03/2005-03/2022).

Strategy	Ann. Alpha	Mkt-RF	Low Risk	Momentum	Size	Value
FM Full	43.23% (0.00**)	0.86	-1.31	0.57	1.23	0.28
FM Top Liquid	37.9% (0.00**)	1.57	-2.09	0.19	0.84	-0.06
FM S&P500	9.14% (0.12)	0.97	-1.32	0.52	0.33	0.68
Shrinkage	37.9% (0.00**)	1.57	-2.09	0.19	0.84	-0.06
Hierarchical RP	2.49% (0.18)	0.00	-0.96	1.00	-1.09	-0.01
In-Sample Vol Control	2.33% (0.00**)	0.10	-0.14	0.02	0.06	0.00
OOS Vol Control	3.15% (0.02*)	0.14	-0.18	0.04	0.06	0.00
Top Liquid $q = 5\%$	71.1% (0.00**)	1.42	-2.05	0.55	1.66	0.06
OOS Vol Control $q = 5\%$	3.27% (0.02*)	0.08	-0.10	0.05	0.08	0.01
Daily Hedged with Futures	45.72% (0.00**)	1.3766	-1.9315	0.4788	1.60	-0.04

We see that contrary to expectations our strategy exhibits $< 100\%$ exposure to the

Momentum Factor itself. It directly supports the implication about balancing out pure return-based Momentum ($d = 1$) and reversal signals ($d = 0$), even in the long-term sense. Our strategy loads heavily on high risk assets, which is also in line with the construction - as the sorting is done on pure return (which is discussed in Future Research Section), we are likely to end up with higher risk assets in the portfolio. However, the outperformance is excessive to this effect. Finally one may note that the strategy is highly leveraged Size factor, attracting many mid-cap and (liquid) low-cap stocks into the portfolio - an effect that vanishes after conducting the OOS scaling.

We finalize the analysis by using the Bayesian Linear Regression to fit the dynamic evolution of alpha of our strategy. Our approach models alpha as a random walk sequential process and regularizes alpha similar to the scheme of Jensen et al. (2021), but does so in the sequential fashion. Namely, we introduce prior knowledge by assuming that actually our alpha is zero mean and stochastic volatility process $\alpha_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\alpha_{t-1}, \sigma_t^2)$ with $\alpha_0 = 0$. Same procedure is done for beta, but centered at 1, as the strategy is long-only. Then we fit the model on obtained strategy performance and get alpha evolution through time - a robust method to identify the strategy performance for the inclusion into the portfolio of existing alpha strategies.

Figure 16: CAPM Alpha Evolution (03/2005-03/2022)

We can see that the **strategy clearly exhibits the stable alpha over time**. If the strategy would be well-known by the investors, we would have the alpha decay - line with negative slope.

Additionally, we provide the plot of compounded outperformance, compared to S&P500. We can clearly see the positively sloped curve, meaning that our final strategy exhibits stable alpha collection, compounded over time and is unlikely to be driven by one period of positive deviation, compounded in the future periods by positive market performance.

Figure 17: Outperformance FM 5% versus S&P500 TR (03/2005-03/2022)

4.9 Subsample Analysis

To support the above conclusion we provide the subsample analysis by rolling the strategy yearly, thus starting at different days of week in different market regimes. We see stable outperformance over all years in terms of alpha and elevated Information Ratio.

Table 7: Subsample Analysis (2005-2022)

Year	FD Liquid $q = 5\%$			OOS Scaled			S&P500 TR
	SR	Alpha BM	IR	SR	Alpha BM	IR	SR
2005	1.13	28.34%	1.47	0.47	13.37%	0.73	0.28
2006	0.55	52.42%	3.63	0.06	2.51%	2.76	-1.12
2007	-0.05	11.44%	0.53	-0.19	0.25%	0.13	0.13
2008	-0.71	6.67%	0.12	-0.81	1.64%	0.45	-0.74
2009	2.41	176.49%	3.68	1.19	4.15%	1.60	0.10
2010	1.81	73.17%	2.36	1.47	2.92%	1.92	-0.95
2011	0.50	80.25%	2.13	0.24	2.63%	1.50	-0.02
2012	3.00	97.73%	3.23	1.58	3.11%	1.45	-0.08
2013	2.74	72.21%	2.30	2.03	6.06%	2.05	3.40
2014	-0.10	16.98%	0.64	0.59	1.11%	1.48	0.81
2015	1.30	91.83%	2.53	0.93	3.07%	2.29	-1.33
2016	1.21	54.74%	2.37	1.22	3.50%	1.87	-0.38
2017	1.63	45.15%	1.61	1.14	2.46%	1.18	2.88
2018	0.36	40.09%	1.21	1.56	4.13%	2.44	-0.77
2019	4.35	225.75%	4.03	2.17	2.63%	1.67	2.39
2020	5.31	278.46%	4.87	3.61	8.84%	3.03	0.08
2021	0.66	48.09%	1.26	0.91	1.02%	1.46	1.66
2022	-0.40	11.27%	0.30	0.57	3.18%	2.13	-0.20

5 Implementation Issues

5.1 Bias Discussion

The presented results aim to be fully out-of-sample and as close to reality as possible. We see only three biases that we should address directly.

First of all, our liquid stocks choice is done in-sample. As discussed throughout the previous Section, this does not leak additional information to our models. Testing of out-of-sample sorting is done additionally, indicating no statistically significant shift in the performance.

Next we should address the trading lag implementation. Throughout all of the outlined results we used 1 day trading lag, meaning that we sort the stocks based on the function of prices up to close of yesterday and trade by the close of today. While this is a robust approach, usually used in the literature, we present the 2-day lag performance for reference.

Figure 18: Cumulative Performance, 2 Days Lag (02/2005-03/2022)

5.2 Data Collection

The data that was used is collected and cleaned by CRSP professionals. For the production implementation we will need to use our own data engineering pipelines. However, as the only data that is needed for weights calculation is the history of prices (as large as possible), the only challenge that we currently note is the need to merge current Bloomberg prices with the ‘permno’ tickers of CRSP. The strategy does not require any additional data, except for publicly available close prices for the set of stocks in our tradeable universe.

5.3 Liquidity

As our main analysis is focused on subsample of 5,000 Top Liquid Stocks, we suppose that the liquidity concerns should not affect the production performance. As our target strategy equally weighs 125 stocks, the average amount in each stock will result to be 0.8%. As our least liquid stock has exhibited \$3,750,395.94 average daily volume, under the assumption of being able to collect 20% of the trades at reasonable cost, one results with the conclusion that the portfolio smaller than \$93.75 mio is able to accommodate such an allocation.

5.4 Transaction costs

Following up on the liquidity concerns, we challenge our 2 bps spread assumption. While the median spread of these 5,000 stocks results to be 0.002% (grouped by average for each stock and averaged cross-sectionally) well below the assumed 0.02%, the upper 90%-quantile results in 1 bps. This supports our conservative assumption and agrees with the overall analysis.

Our future research will be followed by the paper from the same author, focusing on regularization for the transaction costs optimization in Momentum strategies S. Chitsiripanich et al. (2024), which we outline in the next Section.

5.5 Volatility Control

Finally, we want to outline the concerns for tracking error seeking optimization. If one targets not pure outperformance to the benchmark, but also wants to control for downside deviation from it, our experiments do allow for that directly by simple volatility control. However, as the strategy is pure risk premium collection, sacrificing volatility by exogenous approach results in inferior performance. We plan to solve this issue by constant capital allocation with target volatility, but our future research Section outlines the potential areas of improvement here too.

6 Further Research

In this section we outline outstanding questions that we consider to be potentially impactful for further development of this strategy.

- *Return-based sorting.* In the strategy we focus solely on return prediction $\hat{r}_{T+1,i}$ as a sorting variable. The choice of this is motivated by original paper and discussion with Dr. Soros Chitsiripanich. Argument for such choice is that in general the findings do not support any volatility dependence in the Momentum effect. This means that in the debate of sorting by excessive Sharpe or excessive return the latter is more favourable. However, we would like to explore more robust techniques for risk-based attribution of Momentum like Bayesian Linear Regression, similar to Jensen et al. (2021) paper.
- *Dynamic regime choice of d .* The strategy works with fixed amount of retained memory: $d = 0.9$. However, as the market behaves differently in different regimes (mean-reverting vs momentum), one may find different optimal d -values at different subsamples. Our idea is to regularize d to be in the acceptable interval $[0.8; 0.95]$ (range that the author considers to be acceptable) and optimize at each rebalancing period.
- *ARFIMA.* Adding up to the previous section, we would like to follow up on the ARFIMA approach, suggested by the author in Appendix B of the paper. This optimization allows for fitting the optimal d dynamically.
- *Bayesian uncertainty.* As was argued in the section for Volatility Scaling, the OOS Scaling strategy gets out of the optimal allocation for the risk control in the high volatility periods, which is adverse for the Momentum effect. Therefore, the optimal rebalancing might be formulated in Bayesian sense - we want to decrease exposure not when our volatility is high, but when our uncertainty about (potential future) risk premium being statistically significantly far from zero. For this approach we plan to use Bayesian regularization and Uncertainty Quantification.
- *Transaction costs.* We plan to explore transaction costs improvements by following on S. Chitsiripanich et al. (2024).

We thank Dr. Soros Chitsiripanich for the discussion of the ideas and interesting suggestions for the future research.

7 Conclusion

In this replication study, we have improved the basic approaches of the initial paper and introduced additional robustness checks, especially concentrated around Bayesian modeling, which **support the decision to implement this strategy**. The testing out-of-sample for our target *Fractional Momentum* strategy achieved Sharpe Ratio of 1.2663 and Information Ratio of 1.5758 after accounting for market frictions.

We find robustness of the outperformance across the whole sample of data. This indicates excessive risk premium to documented factors in the literature. Moreover, the proposed strategy produces robust results both in Bayesian alpha testing and in the subsample analysis. The result is robust to the hedging scheme, used in 2025-2026 trading setup. We do not experiment with the hyperparameters, aiming to robustly replicate the paper and motivate any changes in the procedure for replication purposes only.

The reason for outperformance is the model-free approach of *fractional differencing* that allows to retain the memory across the whole path. Moreover, this approach allows for differenced data to contain stylized facts of the financial returns, such as heavy tails, conditional heteroskedasticity and non-stationarity. It does not solve the problem of structural breaks that affect hyperparameters settings, which is the topic for further research.

Further research on the topic may be focused on dynamic estimation of the hyperparameter regime with regularization of the admissible set of parameters, which can be done with the Bayesian Machine Learning techniques that would additionally allow for effective risk-management and alpha decay control.

We conclude that the presented approach is robust in the US Stocks universe and represents an improved Momentum risk premium collection technique, being a generalization of the well-documented factor. Therefore, we recommend this strategy for implementation in the portfolio.

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9 Appendices

9.1 A. Full Table of Metrics

Metric	S&P500	EW	Full	S&P Const.	FD 20%	Shrinkage	HRP	FD 5%	Scaled 5%	Hedged
Mean Return (%)	6.27	25.16	44.49	11.25	35.86	35.86	32.07	68.15	7.20	42.87
Standard Deviation (%)	10.45	25.64	30.92	29.65	36.36	36.36	37.06	50.56	5.02	54.34
Skewness	-1.26	18.00	0.50	0.81	0.43	0.43	0.25	1.62	0.30	1.90
Kurtosis	10.91	451.05	8.20	13.57	7.41	7.41	7.86	9.77	40.89	11.15
Maximum Drawdown (%)	-20.82	-28.34	-44.92	-59.01	-59.95	-59.95	-61.91	-59.46	-6.68	-55.97
Sharpe Ratio	0.21	0.82	1.31	0.24	0.88	0.88	0.76	1.27	0.63	0.72
Alpha vs BM (%)	N/A	22.78	44.34	6.49	36.31	36.31	32.87	71.09	3.27	45.72
Alpha p-value	N/A	0.00	0.00	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00
Tracking Error vs BM (%)	N/A	24.68	25.06	27.95	31.91	31.91	32.63	45.11	4.91	49.65
IR vs BM	N/A	0.92	1.77	0.23	1.14	1.14	1.01	1.58	0.67	0.92
Timing Ability Coef	N/A	-2.96	-2.32	-2.00	-6.36	-6.36	-7.45	-5.76	-0.40	-6.19
Timing Ability p-value	N/A	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00

Table 8: OOS Performance Metrics after TC

9.2 B. Example of Holdings

Table 9: Company Identifiers and Names (Part 1).

Company ID	Company Name
12060	GENERAL ELECTRIC CO
12622	H C A HOLDINGS INC
12623	HUNTINGTON INGALLS INDS INC
13124	LAREDO PETROLEUM HOLDINGS INC
13188	POST HOLDINGS INC
13278	HOMESTREET INC
13563	TILE SHOP HOLDINGS INC
13641	DIAMONDBACK ENERGY INC
13812	MARIN SOFTWARE INC
13919	AMBAC FINANCIAL GROUP INC
13921	CUSTOMERS BANCORP INC
14179	ANTERO RESOURCES CORP
14312	HOUGHTON MIFFLIN HARCOURT CO
14456	EAGLE PHARMACEUTICALS INC
14689	AEMETIS INC
14751	VERITIV CORP
15287	CORBUS PHARMACEUTICALS HLD INC
15440	WINGSTOP INC
15623	HOULIHAN LOKEY INC
15921	MANITOWOC FOODSERVICE INC
16021	SILVER RUN ACQUISITION CORP
16086	HERTZ GLOBAL HOLDINGS INC NEW
16158	VERSO CORP
16448	SANDRIDGE ENERGY INC
16522	ORGANOGENESIS HOLDINGS INC
16529	PENN VIRGINIA CORP
16543	VAREX IMAGING CORP
16592	RAMACO RESOURCES INC
16689	PEABODY ENERGY CORP NEW
17073	EARTHSTONE ENERGY INC
17093	METROPOLITAN BANK HOLDING CORP
17126	NEWMARK GROUP INC
17332	VICTORY CAPITAL HOLDINGS INC
17801	CONSTRUCTION PARTNERS INC
17900	TRICIDA INC

Table 10: Company Identifiers and Names (Part 2).

Company ID	Company Name
17956	BERRY PETROLEUM CORP
18065	GARRETT MOTION INC
18224	CONTURA ENERGY INC
18515	BRIGHAM MINERALS INC
18729	COLGATE PALMOLIVE CO
19098	HESS MIDSTREAM L P
19413	ALBERTSONS COMPANIES INC
19632	HIGHPEAK ENERGY INC
19813	B C T G ACQUISITION CORP
19838	NEWHOLD INVESTMENT CORP
19989	RADIUS GLOBAL INFRASTRUCTURE INC
20146	FINTECH ACQUISITION CORP IV
20161	OASIS PETROLEUM INC
20188	CALIFORNIA RESOURCES CORP
20395	C V B FINANCIAL CORP
20522	C B R E ACQUISITION HOLDINGS INC
20568	APRIA INC
20583	CHESAPEAKE ENERGY CORP
20609	LONGEVERON INC
20649	HAYWARD HOLDINGS INC
20654	DUCKHORN PORTFOLIO INC
20844	MOUNTAIN CREST ACQ CORP II
20870	PROMETHEUS BIOSCIENCES INC
23026	FIRSTENERGY CORP
24766	NORTHROP GRUMMAN CORP
34673	NEWPARK RESOURCES INC
50017	RANGE RESOURCES CORP
52337	TENET HEALTHCARE CORP
55597	BRUSH WELLMAN INC
60098	OTTER TAIL POWER CO
65875	BELL ATLANTIC CORP
66739	SWIFT ENERGY CO
75175	M B I A INC
75825	EOG RESOURCES INC
76750	MONRO MUFFLER BRAKE INC
77354	SCHOLASTIC CORP

Table 11: Company Identifiers and Names (Part 3).

Company ID	Company Name
77730	TYSON FOODS INC
78003	VERTEX ENERGY INC
78038	RADIAN GROUP INC
79103	O REILLY AUTOMOTIVE INC
79857	PATTERSON ENERGY INC
79866	SCHNITZER STEEL INDUSTRIES INC
80114	C M G I INC
80415	CENTEX CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS INC
80926	CALLON PETROLEUM CO DEL
81593	WASHINGTON MUTUAL INC
82179	INTEGRA LIFESCIENCES HLDNGS CORP
83520	JAKKS PACIFIC INC
84010	USANA INC
85272	AEHR TEST SYSTEMS
85390	CHILDRENS PLACE RTL STORES INC
85860	BROOKLINE BANCORP INC
86004	UMPQUA HOLDINGS CORP
86233	U S E C INC
87043	QUANTUM CORP
87078	ALLSCRIPTS INC
87759	CHROMALINE CORP
89323	UNITED COMMUNITY BANKS INC GA
89447	CALAVO GROWERS INC
89875	BIOSANTE PHARMACEUTICALS INC
89901	WHITING PETROLEUM CORP NEW
90071	N R G ENERGY INC
90090	SIGNATURE BANK NEW YORK N Y
90162	GENWORTH FINANCIAL INC
90533	W & T OFFSHORE INC
90564	PRESTIGE BRANDS HOLDINGS INC
90988	BROOKDALE SENIOR LIVING INC
91086	ACORDA THERAPEUTICS INC
91161	GREEN PLAINS RENEWABLE ENERGY IN
91237	VONAGE HOLDINGS CORP
91283	R A M ENERGY RESOURCES INC
91579	K B R INC
91683	SALLY BEAUTY HOLDINGS INC
91983	CONTINENTAL RESOURCES INC